

METHODOLOGICAL CHALLENGES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY SCHOOL EDUCATION IN KARAKALPAKSTAN DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

A.Masharipova

Regional center of retraining and professional development of public educators of the Republic of Karakalpakstan Senior Lecturer of the Department of "Pedagogy, Psychology and Educational Technology"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6060928>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th February 2022

Accepted: 10th February 2022

Online: 13th February 2022

KEY WORDS

Preschool education, preschool foundation, preschool age, preschool upbringing, kindergarten, private kindergarten, mobile kindergarten

ABSTRACT

This article includes much information from sphere of preschool education and based on sources about the enrollment of preschool children in preschool education institution and the activities of organization.

On December 29, 2016, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev adopted a resolution "On reforms in the system of preschool education and improvement in 2017-2021." This decision will allow the school to radically reform the system of pre-school education, to reorganize it in line with modern requirements and to create the necessary conditions for the upbringing of children as adults, and to raise the pre-school system to a new level. It is clear that the upbringing of our young people and their comprehensive preparation for school, which will continue our future, is the most important task of today and the key to our future. The President pays special attention to the fundamental improvement of the system of pre-school education,

which is the first and most important link in the upbringing of the younger generation.

It has created the necessary conditions for our people to live a decent life, receive education and acquire a profession in accordance with international standards, and to realize the creative level of our citizens. Based on the tasks set before us today, special attention is paid to the development of pre-school education, especially to the modernization of the quality and effectiveness of education, taking into account the national and international experience. As a result, the material and technical base of pre-school education, methodological support is improved, and advanced pedagogical and information technologies are widely introduced into the teaching process. A

number of decrees and resolutions have been adopted in the country to radically improve the system of preschool education: PD-2707 of December 29, 2016 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the system of preschool education in 2017-202", PD-3261 of September 9, 2017 "On measures to improve the system of preschool education", PD-518 of September 30, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the management of the system of preschool education" numeric decrees can be an example. At the same time, the Republic of Karakalpakstan marked 2018 as the "Year of Preschool Education" and set a goal to increase the coverage of preschool children in preschool education by 45% in the same year and achieved its goal. Today in the Republic of Karakalpakstan the field of preschool education is widely developed. Prior to the launch of the Ministry of Preschool Education, there were a total of 318 preschool educational institutions in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, of which 308 were public, 3 non-public and 7 preschool educational institutions. Today in the Republic of Karakalpakstan there are a total of 543 preschool education centers, including 375 public, 6 private, 22 public-private partnerships, 2 enterprises, 136 non-governmental kindergartens. As of April 1, 2019, the number of children aged 3-7 in the country was 150,974, of which 67,091 children were enrolled in preschool education.

On the base of the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 442-f of May 28, 2018 "On the development of the system of preschool education, increasing the coverage of preschool children in preschool education institutions, the provision of preschool

education to children from low-income families" On June 1, 2018, the State Educational Institution No. 48, located on H. Abdambetov Street, Nukus, was organised. The pre-school education system is designed for children from low-income families. To the organisation children from low-income families, who account for 50 percent of the total number of children, were received free on basic documents. In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 16, 2018 PD-3909 "On measures for the introduction of a multidisciplinary public school with rehabilitation facilities for children in the Aral Sea region" On April 4, 2019, a multidisciplinary public school with a capacity of "Imkon" was launched. And a new type of pre-school education is being introduced in our country. On the basis of mobile groups, the Government adopted a resolution (No. 786, dated 18.09.2019) on the implementation of an experimental project for the provision of preschool education services to schools. According to the resolution, starting from the 2019-2020 academic year, mobile pre-school education groups will be organised in the reconstructed ISUZU HC 40 buses in different districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the provinces. One of the tasks of the mobile group is to create conditions for the full development of children who are not covered by preschool education. Mobile groups accept children from 3 to 7 years of age who do not attend preschool education. Today, the school is taught by 4,769 teachers in preschool education. Of these, 1601 have higher education, 3172 have secondary education and 168 have no education. Of these, there are 3,240 nurses, 711 with higher education

and 2,529 with secondary education. In accordance with the order of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 15, 2018, in order to provide pre-school education with highly educated staff, in the Regional center of retraining and professional development of public educators of the Republic of Karakalpakstan 695 nurses, 173 speech pathologists and 82 psychologists have been trained to provide pre-school education with highly educated specialists. Today, our pre-school education facilities are conducive to the comprehensive development of early childhood and school-age children in accordance with state requirements and state educational traditions, taking into account the individual needs of children. The main goal of pre-school education is to bring up a physically healthy, mentally fit, intellectually developed, logical thinker, spiritually rich, able to express themselves

freely [3:56]. Employees of pre-school educational institutions deeply understand this and hope that our future generations will have national and cultural values, self-awareness, national pride, love for the Motherland, respect for the elderly and people, their parents. Because under the influence of the culture of speech and relationships of people in the circle, the feelings of young children brought up in the kindergarten develop and personal differences begin to appear.

In conclusion, the system of pre-school education is the first stage of continuing education, which is a very responsible and important stage, which imposes great tasks and responsibilities on educators in the education of our young generation.

REFERENCES:

1. «Илк қадам» Мактабгача таълим муассасасининг Давлат ўқув дастури. Тошкент- 2018.
2. “2017-2021 йилларда мактабгача таълим тизимини янада такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2016 йил 29 декабрдаги ПҚ-2707-сонли Қарори.
3. К.Д.Тлеумбетова. “Мектепке шекемги билимлендириш: таъжирийбелер, машқалалар ҳәм раўажланыў перспективалары” атамасындағы Республикалық илимий - әмелий конференциясы.
4. www.Lex.uz